

A Study on Culture in Chinua Achebe's Things Fall Apart

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Abstract

Chinua Achebe is a father of modern African Literature, who was awarded the Nigerian National order of merit Award in 1979. It's the highest academic award in Nigeria. He is a fertile writer and versatile genius of African literature. His work are based on Igbo society, culture, traditions, beliefs etc., Things Fall Apart is the first work by Chinua Achebe which deals and portrays about the most crucial Igbo culture based on ancient African culture that encompasses polytheistic religion, forming tradition and attire and foods. The Igbo society is rich in culture, festivals, ceremonious of southern Nigeria. This study focuses on Achebe's use of Igbo culture tradition as a way of life in Africa.

Keywords: Igbo culture, African Tradition, Myths, music, attire, and cuisine.

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"A true classic of world literature. A masterpiece that has inspired generations of writers in Nigeria, across Africa, and around the world." —Barack Obama

The Igbo cultures are the customs, practices and traditions of the Igbo people of southeastern Nigeria. It contains archaic practices as well as new concepts added into the Igbo people's visual art, music, dance, attire, and cuisine. The Igbo culture is different from other cultures. Because every culture is having its own unique tradition and civilization. The Nigerian culture followed some different types of customs and traditions by belief. Chinua Achebe has explores about the Igbo culture throughout the novel Things Fall Apart. These kinds of culture based novels better examine the pattern for myths followed in their society.

In this regard, the Igbo culture in Things Fall Apart is a symbol of collective existence. Therefore the Nigerian has several and individual groups for their own identity. Throughout the novel, Achebe reveals some traditional cultures and postcolonialism.

This seminal text of Achebe is based on the traditional beliefs and customs of an Igbo village. Achebe has taken many challenges to illustrate the practices of Igbo people. According to the Igbo people, their ideas and practices became essential elements in their everyday lives. African culture ethnically varies from Western culture. Even more, every tribe has its own culture within Africa. Things Fall

Apart is set in the 1890s, and eventually, it portrays the cultural clash between the white colonial government and the Indigenous Igbo people.

In Achebe's *Things Fall Apart*, he uses some Igbo cultures which are explored throughout the particular characters, namely Okonkwo and Ogbuefi Edu. Okonkwo is the protagonist of the novel and influential leader in Umuofia. Achebe says that through the book "No matter how prosperous a man as if he was unable to rule his women and children, he was not a man." Okonkwo's tragedy is the most excellent example of a disaster that takes place with the merger of the east and the west. He cannot bear the yoke of colonization, and he hangs himself. The irony of the fate he is not provided a proper funeral because he just committed suicide. Therefore in Igbo culture, when someone gets committing suicide, it's considered to be the sin in Igbo culture. According to the Igbo society and culture, his suicide scenario is regarded as the sin, and no one should not touch his dead body even through should not stand beside his body.

Things Fall Apart is rich in religious themes, which takes the role of polytheistic in regular life contracts with different furies and gods, which is connected with their Polytheistic. Chukwu is the supreme god in the Igbo religion. Other gods and humans seem to fear Chukwu. Religion plays a predominant role in the Ibo village. One of Achebe's challenges was to illustrate the Ibo's religious system. Even though the Ibo people had little connection with the outside world, they had developed their own beliefs and practices that became essential elements in their everyday lives.

The Ibo religion performed a role in the way they raised their families, communicated, entertained, and governed their society. Naturally, this belief is passed from generation to generation. For instance, the white settlers tried to change their religion to Christianity; the majority of the Ibo people were not willing to change their faith. Religion is one such belief that made the people of Ibo village sticking to their traditional values and strengthening their ancient bond. Different aspects of Igbo religion come up throughout the novel, and several times, doctrine and religious observances play a significant role in the plot.

You say that there is individual supreme God who made heaven and earth," said Akunna on one of Mr. Brown's visits. "We also think in Him and call Him Chukwu. He made all the society and the other gods". "There are no other idols," said Mr. Brown. "Chukwu is the only God, and group the others are false." (*Things Fall Apart* 127)

Chinua Achebe has made out possible with his detailed descriptions of the legal practices, the marriage customs, and community laws of the Igbo people. One example of this is the Week of Peace. The purpose of the 'Week of Peace' is to honor the earth goddess Ani, before the planting of the new crops. During this particular festival occasion, no work is done by the people of the village. They visit their neighbors and have palm-wine.

We live in peace with our associates to honor our great goddess of the earth without whose blessing our crops would not grow. You have committed a great evil....Your wife was at fault, but even if you came into your obi and found her lover on top of her, you would still have committed a great evil to beat her...The harm you have done can ruin the whole clan. The earth goddess whom you have insulted may refuse to give us her increase, and we shall all perish...You will bring to the shrine of Ani tomorrow one she-goat, one hen, a length of cloth and a hundred cowries. (*Things Fall Apart* 22)

This observance is an essential aspect of Igbo society. This particular portrayal gives the reader help to understand the situation better what is happening around the Igbo community. Understanding Igbo culture throws light on the importance of diverse sphere among Nigeria. These are the explanations for what the heavenly and earthly bodies have and give advice on how to behave toward the god, spirits, and one's ancestors.

As a concluding part, *Things Fall Apart* displays the rich culture and beliefs prevalent in Nigeria. Moreover, it stands for the uniqueness of it. The people stood for strength, courage, respect, and wealth. The clash of cultures, tradition and conventions show the familial bonding and closeness of the ethnic group Igbo. Achebe has given space to the Nigerian society through his portrayal of his community and made *Things Fall Apart* not only dedicated to his people rather a universalized one.

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